

INNOVATIVE TECHNIQUES IN WORKING WITH VOCABULARY IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. *Although methodological recommendations have been developed on general guidelines, directions, sources of work on vocabulary in primary education, they cannot yet be called satisfactory. To work on the dictionary, a special lesson is not allocated. It is carried out in the study of all subjects, mainly in connection with the teaching of textbook materials in the native language and reading lessons. In this article, feedback and feedback on the methods of innovation in working with vocabulary in elementary grades will be made.*

Keywords: *innovation, elementary classes, vocabulary, word meaning, abstract words, synonyms, lexicology, methods.*

Lexicology is a section that studies the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. Lexicology studies such as the property of words in vocabulary to express meaning in speech, activity of application, enrichment, depreciation of certain words, withdrawal from consumption, phenomenon of migration of meaning. For this reason, lexicology is the linguistic basis of the methodology for working on vocabulary.

Any speech statement is grammatically interconnected, structured in a place-to-place manner in a certain consistency of words and word combinations corresponding to the content. The richer and more developed a person's vocabulary, the richer his speech will be; a wide opportunity is created for him to clearly and expressively state his opinion. Therefore, the wealth, variety, mobility of the dictionary is an important condition for the successful cultivation of speech in the methodology. To the enrichment of the reader's vocabulary, first of all, the environment that surrounds it, nature, the life of people, reading activities, their communication with adults and peers acts as the main source. As a result of the child's relationship with nature and people, the word, phrase learns pictorial expression, Proverbs, wise words, turns them into his own words.

Works of art are the most convincing source in enriching the vocabulary and speech of readers. In the process of familiarization with works of art in reading lessons, analysis, the vocabulary of students is also enriched by certain topics. For example, if in the process of acquaintance with topics related to the seasons of the year the concepts related to changes in nature, birds, animals, the animal world, Martingale-trees, grass-herbs are formed, then by studying works on the themes of spirituality, good and evil, friendship, one comes to certain conclusions on Human Relations, morality. In the process of reading the text, the meaning of the word is not explained. If the need for it is felt, the attention of readers is shifted by giving a short comment, not distracted by the content of the text. Words used in a portable sense are explained after the text is read.

Since work on vocabulary in native language lessons is aimed at cultivating students' speech, forming literacy, enriching vocabulary, raising the culture of speech, this work begins in the 1st grade in schools and continues throughout the educational process. One of the important

tasks of growing speech at school is the improvement of work on vocabulary, regulation, separation and justification of its main directions, management of the process of enriching the vocabulary of students.

The methodology for working on vocabulary at school provides for four main directions. Enriching the vocabulary of readers, that is, mastering new words, as well as new meanings of certain words that are in the children's dictionary. To find out the vocabulary of the native language, the reader must add 8-10 new words to his dictionary every day, including 4-6 words in the lessons of the native language, that is, master the meaning of these words.

Clarification of the dictionary of readers. This includes the following:

- complete assimilation of the meaning of words that the reader has not mastered thoroughly, that is, the introduction of these words into the text, comparison of words close in meaning, clarification of their meaning by ways of choosing antonyms;
- mastering the ironic meaning of the word, multi-meaning words;
- mastering synonyms of words, edges of meaning of synonymous words;
- mastering the meaning of certain phraseological units.

Activation of vocabulary, that is, the transfer to the active vocabulary of words from the useless dictionary, which readers understand the meaning, but do not use in their speech narration. For this, with the participation of these words, word combinations and sentences are formed, which are used in retelling, conversation, statement and Essay of those who have read.

Transfer of words that are not used in the literary language from the active Dictionary of readers to the useless dictionary. Such words include simple words and phrases that do not fall into the norm of the literary language, which has become absorbed under the influence of the children's speech environment, are used in some literary work and colloquial language, words related to the dialect and social group. Having mastered the concept of the literary language norm, readers begin to use words in the literary language instead of the words explained above. As the skills of the literary language are strengthened, words related to dialect, jargon, simple words and phrases used in colloquial language begin to flow out of the active vocabulary of readers.

The most convincing source in enriching the vocabulary and speech of readers is artistic works. Students in reading lessons Oybek, H.Alimjan, M. Sheikhzade, G'.Ghulam, H. Zulfiq, X.To khtabayev, P. Believer, Q. Muhammad, Z.Diyor, N.Fazilav, T. A. Alakbayev and so on. They master the Uzbek language with the help of highly artistic images. In a reading lesson, children's vocabulary is also enriched at the expense of words on certain topics. Many words are added to their vocabulary, such as cute, sweet, kind, truthful, superstitious, courageous, brave, hardworking, representing moral concepts. In the process of working on the text, they learn multi-meaning words, synonyms, words to work with in a portable sense, some phraseological combinations.

One of the main areas of speech development of Primary School students is work on a word, that is, vocabulary work. The vocabulary work performed in the native language and reading lessons has an important role in increasing the vocabulary of the student. M. R. Lvov informs that half of the new words that primary school students master before Grade IV enter the student's vocabulary through these lessons. "Vocabulary work is not a sheet in the activities of a teacher, but a systematic, well – organized, pedagogically purposefully structured work, which is

connected with the entire section of the Russian language course,” wrote the well-known methodologist scientist A. V. Tekuchev.

The stages of vocabulary work can be expressed as follows: 1) explanation of the meaning of the word, 2) activation of the word, 3) application of the word in speech.

Activating the vocabulary of students is one of the most important areas of vocabulary work, which is performed in the native language and reading lessons. Therefore, the teacher's task is to help the reader master the field of conjugation and application of inactive words in order to transfer inactive words from the reader's dictionary to the active vocabulary Reserve. Even if the reader uses a word only once in his retelling the story, conversation, letter, statement, essay, this word is considered activated. Mastering a word consists in knowing its meaning, compactness and scope of application.

Meaningful words(synonyms) are words that express one common concept (meaning), the pronunciation of which is different in writing. Synonyms differ among themselves in terms of additional meaning edge, emotional coloring, application. From the words that form a large, great, great, excellent, dear, huge, giant, giant synonymous line, the word great is used both in relation to a specific concept and in relation to an abstract concept, comprehending a broad concept. The words great, great, excellent, substantial, huge are used in relation to objects whose size is much larger, and the words giant, stately, are used in relation to objects whose size is too large. Large little used. The giant is typical of the biblical style and is mainly applied to the place, construction. Synonyms enrich the language from the lexical side, so it is very important to work with such words. The more synonyms a person has in his vocabulary, the more his linguistic expressiveness increases.

It is necessary to explain to the reader the meaning of a new word, to achieve its correct understanding of the word. To do this, the teacher must know the methods of explaining the meaning of the word and use them appropriately. M. R. Lvov distinguishes the following methods of explaining the meaning of a word: visual, contextual, bringing synonyms, giving a logical definition, detailed description, bringing an antonym, analyzing the structure of the formation of a word. In the textbooks” native language “and” reading book " a number of words are found that are incomprehensible to students and are inactive in their speech. When activating the dictionary of readers, it is necessary to work mainly on these words. The activation of the reader's dictionary consists of the following main stages:

1. Explaining the meaning of a word using one or more methods:
 - a) using context;
 - b) using the meaning of the same word;
 - d) using the antonym of the same word;
 - e) in a descriptive way (using a dictionary or independently of the teacher himself).
2. Reading and writing the word (work on the correct pronunciation and spelling of the word).
3. So work on examples of application of Z (ready-made word combinations and work on sentences). The teacher introduces students to ready-made vocabulary and sentences in which the studied words are applied. Some of them can be written without saying.
4. Work on the semantic connections of the word. Exercises that teach students to distinguish and master the paradigmatic connections of words help them to enrich their

vocabulary. Such exercises form the ability to select the desired word, accurately convey the content of the sentence, understand the meaning edges of the word.

5. Word combination and sentence formation independently with the participation of the studied words.

Words incomprehensible to readers, which are found in the primary school mother tongue and reading book, are different in their content nature. Therefore, when explaining the meaning of these words, it is necessary to choose the most effective method in accordance with their nature. At this point, we will outline our ideas about choosing an effective way to explain the meaning of a word using the example of words in several textbooks. The meaning of words denoting an abstract concept can be explained using images. (See more about this: let's give a couple of examples.

The word justice can be figuratively explained as follows: "readers, justice is the same attitude towards people. Justice is like pros. (The teacher shows a picture of the scales.) When the same load is placed on both circuits of the scale, its two circuits are equal. When a heavier load is placed on one circuit, one circuit of the scales is high and one circuit is low. now I will give an example from life. For example, a father has 2 sons. Father brought 4 apples from the market. It will be fair if both boys give 2 apples. It will be unfair if he gives one Apple to one son and three to the other son."

The word dare can be explained figuratively as follows: "readers, Dare is a job that is done without fear of risks, difficulties. In life you will have to dare a person without much. For example, if your tooth hurts, you should dare to go to the dentist. Or if you are given a difficult example in mathematics, you should also dare to solve it. Courage, pupils, can be likened to a horse jumping over a cliff. Because it takes a lot of courage, courage to jump over a cliff. Readers, if you act with courage, not afraid of difficulties in life, you will achieve your intended goal."

Explaining the meaning of the word is not yet the first step in enriching the vocabulary of readers. In order for the word to become the "own property" of the reader, that is, to enter the active vocabulary, it is required to carry out a large work. Experience in speech cultivation shows that template and unplanned in this regard cannot be allowed. For each lesson, consistent, thorough, constant work should be carried out on the word to be planned.

Explaining the meaning of words enriches the vocabulary of readers, cultivates speech. The terms of the subjects taught in elementary grades are also included in the line of words that must be explained. Explaining the meaning of the terms helps to better understand the concept that this word means. For example, with a meaningful explanation of the term subject, readers will learn that the subject is used in a broad sense, that all things, phenomena, concepts in nature are called subjects. It helps them in the rapid interpretation of terms such as noun, adjective, number, verb. It should take very little time to explain the meaning of the word and not distract the attention of students from the main topic of the lesson. To do this, the teacher, in the process of preparing for each lesson, determines the words, the meaning of which should be explained, the most convenient ways to explain it, and in which place of the lesson the explanation should be made.

Conclusion. Some words that are first encountered in texts in reading books, which children do not know the meaning of, are explained before reading the text. In the process of reading the text, it is necessary to put an end to explaining the meaning of the word. If the need

arises to explain a word at the time of reading the text, then the meaning of this word is briefly explained, without distracting the attention of readers from the content of the text. Figurative words and literary speech inscriptions used in a portable sense are explained after reading the text, since their meaning is well understood from the content of the text, from the context. Especially when parables are read, words used in it in an allegorical, portable sense cannot be explained before or during the reading process of a work.

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